

EMERGE

Equipping Minoritized and
Emerging Research Institutions
to Grow Their Enterprises

Assessing the Impact of Research Development: A Guide for Research Development Professionals

A peer-reviewed EMERGE resource from the NORDP Consultants Program

By: Kimberly Eck, MPH, PhD, Karen Fischer, MBA, Enas Albataineh, PhD, Aisha A. Alvarez, PhD, Susan Carter, JD, Pamela A.G. Clarke, Marta Collier-Youngblood, MA, Dorothy Daley, MS, CGMS, Jayanta Das, PhD, Margaret Farrow, Melissa A. Harrington, PhD, Triscia W. Hendrickson, PhD, James Kohler, PhD, Rachel McBride-Montesdeoca, EdD, Eric A. Mintz, PhD, Ishita Mukerji, PhD, Marcia Straughn, PhD, RN, CNE, Kimberley R. Sudler, Ed.D, MBA, Christopher Theriot, DBA, CFRE, Frances Williams, PhD, Tamika S. Williamson, CPA, MBA, Alicia T. Wyatt, EdD

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About the NORDP Consultants Program

The NORDP Consultants Program is dedicated to increasing the diversity of the national research ecosystem by providing research development services to minority-serving institutions (MSIs) and emerging research institutions (ERIs) at no cost to the institution.

The program pairs research development professionals with investigators and research leadership to:

1. Strengthen researchers' capacity to compete for external funding,
2. Enhance research enterprise infrastructure and capacity,
3. Inspire institutional research cultures, and
4. Magnify the visibility and competitive reputation of MSIs and ERIs in the research enterprise.

Executive Summary

Assessing and communicating the impact of research development is increasingly important for research development professionals and research leadership within institutions of higher education. This article sets forth a framework for categorizing research development metrics, explores realistic ways of assessing the impact of research development, makes recommendations for the research development professionals charged with assessing the impact of the research development function, and discusses challenges and mitigation strategies. It is a first step in documenting the research development field's current practices in assessing the impact of research development. Although this adaptable framework can apply to research development in almost any type of institution, we make special notes for considerations among emerging research institutions (ERIs) and minority serving institutions (MSIs).

Key Recommendations:

1. Capture, report, and communicate activity metrics annually.
2. Capture, report, and communicate impact metrics annually as a complement to activity metrics.
3. Capture relevant quality or process improvement metrics. Report and communicate as needed.

Target Audience

Primary audience: Research development professionals

Secondary audience: Research enterprise leaders

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Introduction

Research Development (RD) plays a substantive role in the research enterprise, frequently providing diverse services that are highly tailored to increase the competitiveness of grant applications and faculty success. These services are typically not a part of the mandatory workflow or proposal submission and award processing, but should be documented and validated to show the **impact** of RD. Institutions of higher education (IHE) leadership increasingly seek to understand the impact of RD, that is, how the research enterprise is better off because of RD, and RD leaders need to be able to articulate the impact on the faculty, the institution, the community, and beyond.

Metrics are quantifiable assessments that organizations use to monitor and improve their performance over time. They can be utilized to inform decision-making about strategy, priorities, resources, and services. Within the context of research at an IHE, activity metrics (i.e. how many) for core services are frequently monitored to approximate office workload and comparative growth or retraction of the research enterprise during a defined time period. For example, activity metrics could include the number of proposals submitted by the pre-award office, the number of protocols reviewed by the institutional review board, or the number of electronic notices of awards processed by the office of sponsored programs. Comparing these activities year-over-year would be a reasonable starting point for monitoring workload and the size of the research enterprise. Quality of these services may be assessed through a faculty feedback survey sent to all users, which could be a broad swath of faculty and other investigators.

Assessing impact and quality requires a thoughtful approach given that activity metrics are a poor indicator of RD workload, especially in an emerging research institution (ERI) where grant seeking is not yet widespread and an individual investigator may require years of support to secure an externally-sponsored award.

This article sets forth a framework for categorizing research development metrics, explores realistic ways of assessing the impact of research development, makes recommendations for the research development professionals charged with assessing the impact of the research development function, and discusses challenges and mitigation strategies. It is a first step in documenting the research development field's current practices in assessing the impact of research development.

Background and the Challenge of Measuring Research Development Impact

Eck and Roney (2022) define research development as "... a function that seeks to grow research or increase the research reputation of an institution." They highlight that although most research development professionals provide services related to finding funding, facilitating collaborations, and proposal development support, each individual and each office provides a slightly different suite of services. Importantly, the authors also note that most research development professionals spend time "capturing and monitoring proposal and award metrics as well as defining and capturing other types of success metrics."

Often viewed as optional, and a sometimes misunderstood function within the research ecosystem, research development professionals have, at a minimum, been asked to help justify the investment in this role since its inception. The audience for this justification often includes research and academic leadership, institutional executives, and financial managers. Activity metrics, described in detail below, have been and remain foundational metrics, yet RD professionals quickly recognized that these measures do not always capture their true impact and are not direct indicators of program service or quality. This mismatch remains, but many research development offices have expanded their reporting to better advocate for the function within their unique institutional setting.

Complicating matters, RD is sometimes viewed as a contributing, but insufficient, factor in achieving critical research enterprise outcomes. Most RD activities need action and significant contributions from others - often faculty and other key research leaders - in order to achieve the intended outcome. The indirect relationship between RD effort and outcomes makes assessing RD impact more challenging and highly dependent on the institutional context.

Input, Data Sources, and Methods

Given the above challenges in defining and measuring RD impact, we consulted multiple sources of insight to inform our shared understanding. In addition to many informal discussions, conference presentations, and our collective experiences, two formal groups provided substantial input and helped to shape the synthesis and frameworks below: participants at the 2025 Advancing Research Impact in Society (ARIS) conference in April 2025 in San Juan, Puerto Rico and the 2025 NORDP Consultants Program Annual Meeting in June 2025 in Atlanta, GA.

What Counts? Crowd-Sourced Perspectives on RD Impact

The authors presented the above background and the draft framework for considering research development metrics at the 2025 ARIS conference. During the session, the authors crowd-sourced input from the attendees, which included approximately 40 broader impact and research development professionals, using Mentimeter, a web-based survey tool. Respondents were invited to scan a QR code or enter a numerical code linked to a webpage where they could submit responses via Mentimeter. Respondents were able to submit multiple responses. When asked, “*What metrics capture the impact of research development?*,” the authors received 227 responses from 36 distinct participants representing a range of institutional types and disciplines. These responses were grouped by common themes, with the most frequently suggested themes presented in Table 1.

Table 1: “What metrics capture the impact of research development⁴¹ ?”

Responses from the 2025 ARIS Conference (Displayed If Frequency > 6)

Theme	Frequency
Count of activity	21
Awards	19
Research Impact of Award	18
Case study / storytelling	15
Proposals	14
Students	14
External Partners	9
Collaboration	9
Faculty Feedback	8
Career / Retention	8

From Ideas to Insights: Grouping and Illustrating RD Impact Metrics

The lead authors then presented the metric-gathering background and a refined framework for considering research development metrics at the 2025 NORDP Consultants Program Annual Meeting. The June 2025 session included 45 research enterprise leaders¹ and staff from emerging research institutions (ERI) and minority serving institutions (MSI). During the session, attendees were invited to discuss the framework and join the authorship team by contributing their metric-related perspectives to this article.

An early draft of this article was organized into eight sections. Attendees self-sorted into eight groups, each assigned to one section for review. Over 90 minutes, groups read the draft section, discussed caveats, gaps, and additional examples to enhance the content. Finally, the group made contributions to the text that was housed in a shared working document.

After the meeting, authors could continue adding examples and were invited to contribute to any section. The lead authors then edited the document for clarity, consistency, and flow with support from other volunteer editors before sending the document for peer review. All authors were invited to review the near-final draft for agreement and copyediting.

Benefit and limitations

The lead authors chose to prioritize lived experiences documented by experienced RD professionals rather than collecting quantitative data or qualitative information at arms-length. This approach offers the benefit of a rich, consensus-based perspective informed by decades of experience. However, the limitation of this approach is that we cannot present quantitative summaries, conduct tests for statistical significance, or otherwise measure agreement numerically. To these ends, the framework and synthesis represent an important and foundational contribution to conceptualizing RD impact measurement that can be later explored with greater academic rigor and expanded through empirical validation. In the short term, these resources are offered to inspire RD professionals as they articulate the value of their service to the research enterprise.

¹ Provosts, Vice Chancellors, VPs for Research and research support staff from Sponsored Research, Research Administration, Research Development), and investigators engaged in research transformation (faculty, postdocs, research project staff).

A Structured Approach to RD Assessment

This section is organized to provide a practical framework for measuring RD impact. It begins with an overview of three primary types of metrics: activity metrics, impact metrics, and quality and process improvement metrics. For each metric type, we outline its purpose, offer guidance on how to select appropriate measures, describe approaches for measurement and reporting in various institutional contexts, and conclude with a table of common examples to illustrate application.

Types of Metrics for Measuring RD

Research development metrics can be grouped into one of three categories: 1) activity metrics, 2) impact metrics, and 3) quality and process improvement metrics. **Activity metrics** capture counts, or 'how many' or 'how much' an activity occurred, like how many proposals were submitted or how many awards were granted. **Impact metrics** reflect how the research ecosystem has improved because of research development, recognizing RD alone is rarely the exclusive cause of the impact. **Quality improvement metrics** draw on participant feedback (often from faculty) to inform enhancements of future RD offerings; while **process improvement metrics** focus on indicators of efficiency and effectiveness.

Exploring Activity Metrics

I. PURPOSE

Although they have significant limitations, assessing the impact of research development often begins with activity metrics. These metrics provide relatively simple captures of activity that track 'how many' or 'how much'. Because they are straightforward, these metrics are easier to monitor over time and can be aggregated across services, programs, and multiple years. While they offer only basic information and may fail to capture important nuances or true impact, they often align with administrators' primary interests, particularly at institutions where research development is a relatively new function.

II. HOW TO SELECT

Most research development offices track and report the number and total budget of supported proposals and resulting awards. However, selecting, capturing, and reporting appropriate activity counts is more complex than it appears. These decisions are influenced by several factors and should be informed by interest from leadership and key stakeholders, institutional priorities, success stories, and the RD workload. See [Table 2](#) for examples of activity metrics.

III. HOW TO MEASURE

There are many ways to measure activity, but the most important principle is to capture what you are doing. Some guiding principles are as follows:

1. For multifaceted RD functions, consider tracking activity metrics across all programs, services, and events by documenting the number of faculty engaged - this can serve as a summative, function-wide metric.
2. Capture RD **staff effort** by documenting the number of hours, meetings, or training provided to faculty and research staff.

3. Capture **engagement** by documenting the number of participants or attendees for each significant program, service, or event series.
4. When feasible, collect more detail than you expect to report. For example, you might record attendee names and departments for a training event, even if you only plan to report the total number of participants. This additional information can be invaluable for ad hoc reporting requests.

A note on institutional data: Senior research officers frequently report institutional activity metrics, including total research expenditures as reported to the Higher Education Research & Development (HERD) survey, sponsored research expenditures, award amounts, and proposal totals for the entire institution. These institutional metrics are not discussed in this article, which focuses on assessing the impact of research development more directly.

IV. HOW TO REPORT

Activity metrics should be standardized and easily repeatable for long-term tracking. Depending on institutional needs, activity metrics may be stratified by college or school, funder, funding program, or discipline to present a more targeted view. These metrics should be reported annually at the close of the institution's fiscal year or calendar year, using simple, standardized visualizations to show year-over-year trends and when possible, five-year summaries.

For annual reporting, proposal-to-award conversion will always be partially incomplete due to the time between proposal and award. Note this misalignment and indicate what proposals are pending. A reasonable assumption is that proposals with no response 18 months after submission are declined, document this assumption. Very few proposals will be funded after 18 months unless other communication from the funder is received.

Historical and current data should be stored in a shared electronic workspace with version control and multi-user access. Key definitions of what is included or excluded should be recorded and reviewed annually.

Common Examples

Table 2: Examples of Activity Metrics

Category	Metric or Narrative Examples
Participants, events, and time	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of participants in research development programming Number of trainings provided by research development staff Number of proposal development and grantsmanship workshops hosted by the research development office per year Number of hours spent by research development staff on supporting a proposal Number of targeted funding notifications sent Number of meetings with faculty
Proposals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of proposals submitted to external sponsors that received research development support Dollar amount of proposals that received research development support Number of proposals submitted and those awarded by college and faculty rank Number of proposals that received peer review before final submission
Awards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Percentage of submissions not funded that received research development support Percentage of submissions that resulted in awards that received research development support Dollar amount of awards that received research development support Success rate by number of proposals, by status, sponsor name, sponsor type, project type, PI/Co-PI department, complexity grade

Exploring Impact Metrics

I. PURPOSE

Impact metrics highlight the contributions that research development makes to the research community beyond simple activity counts. They help contextualize activity metrics, highlight non-financial successes, connect research development to the institutional mission and priorities, and even demonstrate benefits beyond the institution. Impact metrics paint a picture of how the research ecosystem has been improved, strengthened, or elevated through RD activities. While they provide deeper insights, impact metrics often require more time to collect, lack uniformity for comparison, and may not apply in all circumstances.

II. HOW TO SELECT

Generally, research development relies on a carefully selected subset of impact metrics that best illustrate the benefits it provides. At least some qualitative “metrics,” (i.e. case studies, storytelling, and/or impact statements) should be used to complement and explain activity metrics. Institutional priorities, leadership interest, and culture will influence whether or not metrics related to students, trainees, internal collaboration, or external partners are used. Capturing one or more of these impact metrics must be weighed against the time required to collect and track this information. Program evaluation frameworks and tools, such as logic models and the payback framework (Buxton & Hanney, 1996) can help structure what data to collect and how to communicate about it.

To show impact, think beyond annual reports that few stakeholders will read. Elevate the voices of those who have benefitted from your services to key leaders and decision makers. For example, showcase an outstanding student researcher at a board of trustees meeting, or invite a researcher who is a good communicator and has exciting research to give a brief presentation at a meeting of the President’s cabinet. Make sure your marketing office knows about important successes in research, publishes stories on your web page, and puts out press releases. Track positive media stories as an impact of research development. Consider the impact on the stakeholders and how you’ll know whether or not the impact was sustained. See Table 3 for examples of impact metrics.

III. HOW TO MEASURE

Some impact metrics are ideally captured during or soon after a program, service, or event concludes; while others may not emerge until significant time has passed. Therefore, creating systematic ways of capturing short-term and long-term impacts are needed. For example, collecting progress and impact reports for seed grant awardees for several years following the conclusion of the seed award.

Identify impact metrics that reflect the quality, influence, and societal contribution of research, not just its quantity. Examples include:

1. Societal outcomes (e.g., policy change, community engagement, patent adoption).
2. Interdisciplinary or cross-sector partnerships.
3. Faculty engaged in research with other universities, national labs, industry

and foundation partners (e.g., quantify the number of faculty engaged in joint appointments, faculty fellowships, collaborative research grants and monthly meetings with the external partner).

4. Student engagement with external partners via internships and experiential learning (e.g., student research involvement and career pathways).
5. Research communications (e.g., number of articles published on faculty accomplishments and awards, faculty research podcasts, local and national news coverage). If possible, work with your institution to capture growth and research productivity in the tenure and promotion process.

Data should be stored in a shared electronic workspace where multiple users have access. Key definitions of what is included and excluded should be recorded and reviewed annually.

IV. HOW TO REPORT

Remember, activity metrics (e.g., number of grants) only tell part of the story - impact metrics illustrate the value of research to society and alignment with the institution's mission. Develop narratives and metrics that communicate the societal, institutional, and academic impact of funded research that was supported by research development to strengthen advocacy, donor engagement, and public trust.

Annually, position impact metrics alongside activity metrics to explicitly show connections between RD efforts and positive outcomes within the research enterprise. For example, include an **Impact Highlights** section in annual research or institutional effectiveness reports. Formalizing the process ensures consistency, visibility, and accountability. Suggested formats include: infographics or dashboards for quick visual insights; embedded case study boxes; and year-over-year trend comparisons.

Consider creating multiple formats for annual reporting. Impact reporting must resonate with internal and external stakeholders, each of whom values different kinds of information, e.g. executive summaries for leadership, briefs with discipline-specific outcomes for department-level, and public-facing stories for newsletters, websites, and social media. You might also consider creating a research development dashboard that is visual, narrative-integrated reporting in order to drive home both scope and significance of research activity that includes: activity metrics, impact metrics, and qualitative highlights.

Common Examples

Table 3: Examples of Impact Metrics

Category	Metric of Narrative Examples
Case study / storytelling	Case studies or storytelling are an essential aspect of assessing and capturing research impact. Research development case studies and stories begin with the description of a challenge or problem, describe how research development contributed to or led the development and implementation of a solution (often with partners), and the outcome or improvements that resulted from that solution.
Faculty success stories, case studies, or testimonials	Collect annually to illustrate how research funding or development support led to: tangible outcomes (e.g., community health improvements, environmental policy shifts); long-term partnerships; career advancement of junior faculty, trainees, or students. Stories engage stakeholders (boards, donors, the public) and humanize data that might otherwise be dry.
Social justice or health equity and under-represented communities	Include metrics and narratives that reflect institutional values and commitments, particularly in public-facing research.
Participant feedback	Impact Statements and Thank You's: case studies, faculty impact statements and notes of appreciation are sometimes the most revealing and authentic assessments of impact that can be captured for research development. Participants, often researchers, are uniquely positioned to describe the impact that a research development program, service, or staff member has had on their career, project, or research agenda, in a meaningful way.
Researcher productivity and reputational impact	Effective research development programs may need to support faculty to publish their scholarship in academic journals. This support could be through awards of release time or summer salary to focus on collecting data and writing the manuscript, writing support clubs or bootcamps, or simply covering the journal publication charges. A good metric to assess the impact of these supports is tracking the number of publications or scholarly products for supported individuals, departments and the institution. To assess the impact of these initiatives more broadly and over a longer period of time, calculating an "h-index" for departments or the institution as a whole demonstrates reputation impact as this measure incorporates both the numbers of publications and number of times they are cited.

Category	Metric of Narrative Examples
Students and Trainees	Metrics related to how research development contributed to the student experience and/or enabled student and trainee research can be incredibly impactful depending on the institutional context. Student-related metrics could include: the number of students who engage in undergraduate research as a result of research-development supported proposals and other initiatives or the number of NSF Graduate Research Fellowship Program proposals supported by the research development function.
Internal collaborations	Identifying internal collaborations, typically among researchers, facilitated by the research development function related to internal collaboration could include: the number of researchers included on multi-investigator proposals, the number of networking events, or the number of one-on-one introductions made.
Interdisciplinary teams	Visibility into who's collaborating and where promotes institutional alignment and recognition of emerging research areas. Track number of interdisciplinary grant proposals submitted/funded; cross-departmental or cross-college collaborations; and co-authorship across disciplines or schools. To celebrate and normalize collaboration across silos, add an "Interdisciplinary Highlights" section in annual research development or sponsored programs reports and include: number of interdisciplinary proposals and awards; success stories from new centers or research clusters; examples of cross-sector or translational research outcomes.
Economic impact	Number of invention disclosures tech transfer protocols for the university.
Monetary support	Amount of dollars going directly to students and other trainees: internships, wages, scholarships, participant support cost; amount of funds reimbursing payroll for faculty/staff salary and benefits (excluding summer supplemental pay).
Strategic external partners	Identify external collaborations facilitated by the research development function: the number of external partners that participated in events; the number of external partners that participated on proposals supported by the research development function; and the number of universities, industry, national labs, corporations, and/or foundations that contributed to research collaboration amongst faculty, research staff (research scientists, research assistants), students, and other trainees.
Research culture (on and off campus)	Identify the community partners included on proposals. Collaborate with other campus units to collect data to support the RD goals and mission. Consider tracking vendors, student matriculation through research experiences into workforce, and faculty/staff exit interview data to improve RD outputs.

Category	Metric of Narrative Examples
Participant knowledge and self-efficacy	Participants in a research development program, e.g. training for grant seeking, may be asked to respond to a short survey that captures the improvement in knowledge and self-efficacy, referring to an individual's belief in their ability to successfully achieve a specific goal. Because few validated measures exist that are specific to research development programs and services, RD professionals often rely on a bespoke set of questions about the content and goals of the program.
Pay it forward / mentorship success	Develop metrics to measure faculty engagement including the faculty 'type' / 'category' mentors junior faculty: capture the faculty type who stay during the summer to engage in research/outreach activities; the faculty type who review proposals with or without "incentives"; the faculty type who co-author with junior faculty, trainees, and students on and off campus.
Faculty development	Faculty progression related to their research, including leadership in Research Centers, increased collaboration, and mentoring success. These indicators can provide a holistic evaluation of research development capacity.

Exploring Quality and Process Improvement Metrics

I. PURPOSE

Quality and process improvement metrics are aimed at capturing information to assess and improve the quality or process of a research development program or service. These metrics are highly tailored to the specific program or service and potential improvements and are primarily used to inform decision-making about and improve the structure, nuances, and type of research development programs and services. Capturing these metrics may be limited to a concentrated period of assessment, e.g. during a pilot project or before, after a change in the program or service, or after an event.

II. HOW TO SELECT

Quality and process improvement metrics should be tailored to the specific program, service, and/or the desired area of improvement. Stakeholder input, both iterative and longitudinal, contributes to relevant quality improvement processes. Appropriate metrics serve both accountability and improvement purposes. This type of assessment aligns research development metrics with institutional mission, strategic goals, and accreditation standards. See Table 4 for examples.

III. HOW TO MEASURE

Quality assessments often rely on short surveys that ask about potential areas for improvement using a combination of forced response and open-ended questions. Process improvements are more likely to rely on metrics documented by staff during the study period. Consider tracking:

1. Both process and outcome indicators - these balanced metrics reveal not just what was achieved, but how.
2. Integrate continuous improvement frameworks to provide structure for data-informed change in research development practices.
3. Regularly survey faculty on satisfaction with proposal development consultations and other research development activities.
4. Establish faculty-led assessment committees or working groups for research development in order to encourage sharing of best practices and regular reporting and reflection cycles - this engages stakeholders and sustains momentum.

Data should be stored in a shared electronic workspace where multiple team members have access. Key definitions of what is included and excluded should be recorded and reviewed annually.

How To Report

Report quality and process improvement metrics when novel (e.g. as major changes are undertaken and improvements are observed). Consider audience interest when sharing these metrics. Unless a program or service had a particularly visible pain point or widely-recognized deficiency, incremental quality and process improvements may be best suited to those working very closely or within the research administration enterprise. Consider creating internal dashboards to monitor and share real-time progress toward research goals. This improves transparency, engagement, and decision-making.

Common Examples

Table 4: Examples of Quality and Process Improvement Metrics

Metric Name	Example
Participant feedback / improvement suggestions	Formal and informal research development programming feedback may be collected systematically or through ad hoc processes and sometimes offered as an unsolicited comment. Regardless, feedback can range greatly from suggestions for new processes, different timing, varied applicability of topics, to how engaging the speakers were. Depending on the assessment tool, feedback may be quantitative, qualitative, or both.
Efficiency	Occasionally, the research development function may undertake a special project to improve the efficiency (e.g. less time, fewer hours spent, less manual work, fewer iterations) of a process. For example, producing a weekly newsletter featuring relevant funding opportunities rather than spending out individual funding opportunities to one faculty member at a time. These efficiency metrics are highly tailored to the project and improvements sought..

Common Challenges and Other Considerations

Below we describe some of the common challenges and other considerations that may be encountered when assessing the impact of research development and offer a few potential mitigation strategies.

Table 5: Commons Challenges, Key Points, and Mitigation Strategies

Potential Challenges	Key Points	Tips and Mitigation Strategies
An audience-of-one	<p>RD impact reports may have a small readership, e.g. a small group of stakeholders or even a single person (e.g. chief research officer (CRO), President, Provost, Financial Officer) who chooses whether and what to communicate to the campus and institutional leadership about the impact of research development.</p> <p>An audience-of-one may not have the appropriate background to understand the key points.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand the different types of leadership and their responsibilities at the institution. Assessments and communication should depend on who you are reporting to and will vary depending on the interests and passions of the audience-of-one (ex. a Provost may be passionate about faculty and students so provide metrics/examples about how research impacts faculty and students. The President will be interested in the reputation of the university and monetary impact of research, including viable patents/companies). Hone impact metrics to ensure their interests are captured. You may need to educate the audience-of-one about the importance of research and research enterprise metrics. In some cases the audience of one may be 'negatively' focused, i.e. more concerned about threats than opportunities. If that is the case, you need to let them know how the issues will negatively impact what they care about. In other words, let them know that 'if we don't improve our processes...xxx could happen'. Incorporate examples and narratives of success into the annual report. Equip your audience with headline talking points. Get to know your peers, figure out common interests, and work with them to bring ideas to leadership.

Potential Challenges	Key Points	Tips and Mitigation Strategies
<p>Work in progress updates vs. assessing RD impact</p>	<p>Some leaders may desire more frequent updates, which focus on ongoing activity and workload balancing. These work-in-progress updates serve a different purpose than RD impact assessments.</p> <p>There are no standard measures regarding assessing workload (such as number of proposals per person doing proposal development) and are not always available.</p> <p>Metrics are instrumental in moving the needle and telling the story, but workload considerations and standards can be difficult to measure.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Even though work-in-progress updates may provide ample visibility to activity, communicate that it is useful to report on impact annually. ■ Work-in-progress updates (as opposed to impact assessments) can be done frequently, even more so in a rapidly changing environment with a high level of uncertainty. ■ Goals should be established with leadership so metrics can be tracked towards those goals. Goals can be determined from existing projects and grants, especially if there are grants that are supporting the research enterprise and/or student support. ■ Create assessments that can be continuous. These measures can be both qualitative and quantitative. ■ Find ways to conduct real time reporting that shows need and alignment with overall goals.
<p>Investment in collecting metrics</p>	<p>Collecting metrics requires time, sometimes social capital, and occasionally may incur actual costs.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Measuring everything is rarely possible. ■ Start with thoughtfully selected metrics using the recommendations above and refine over time. ■ Measurement should be intentional and driven by institutional goals. ■ Institutional knowledge should be part of the currency; know where the data is housed at your institution and who has it; collaborate to capture the metrics that are needed: establish connections between offices, centers, and other units in order to obtain data. ■ Read final reports from institutional wide task forces that potentially focus on research issues. (ex. accreditation metrics for reports) and incorporate those into your reporting.

Potential Challenges	Key Points	Tips and Mitigation Strategies
The unquantifiable	Some RD impacts are not quantifiable. RD may have had a significant impact on one person or one project that doesn't lend itself to quantification.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use case studies, storytelling, and impact statements to qualitatively document the unquantifiable impacts. Interview researchers to discuss how an RD project shaped their thinking pertaining to RD topics. Include sections in activity evaluation for participants to include quotes/testimonials about the impact of the activity.
Sharing credit among staff across offices	RD is a team sport. RD work is always in partnership with someone, e.g. faculty, RD professionals from other offices, or corporate and foundation relations staff. RD professionals must report metrics to describe the work they supported while others may simultaneously take credit for the same work for similarly valuable contributions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaborative work is inherent to the research enterprise. Many people contribute to every success and all are entitled to report it. Reporting on activity, proposals, awards, partnerships, etc. does not mean taking sole credit for the activity. Partners/collaborators should be acknowledged when reporting successes and impact related to joint efforts (in presentations, annual reports, etc.).
Misalignment between RD quality and RD metrics	Many RD metrics are a poor indicator of the quality of RD programs and services. Having fewer awards than last year may have no relation to the quality of RD support they received.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Be clear about what your metrics do and do not measure. Examine quantity with specific quality improvement metrics and assess plans. Base metrics on things your office is doing to increase/enhance research outcomes rather than the actual outcome. Unquantifiable metrics may be beneficial for this.

Potential Challenges	Key Points	Tips and Mitigation Strategies
<p>Outsized expectations from leadership for results</p>	<p>Some leaders may expect significant and nearly immediate success in activity metrics but that type of change may take years.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Report on activity metrics. ▪ Explain and re-explain realistic timelines for proposal preparation, submission, reviewer feedback, resubmission, and success rates. ▪ Report on meaningful impact metrics. ▪ Use data from previous outcomes/years to right-size their expectations. ▪ Educate them with facts and best practices that they may not be aware of, that may assist in their understanding. It may also give them a perspective of what resources it would actually take to achieve what they are asking.

Strategic Recommendations for RD Impact Assessment

Recommendation 1:

Capture, report, and communicate activity metrics annually.

Activity metrics are a core component of annual RD reporting. Present the number and total amount of proposals and awards supported by RD along with selected activity counts that reflect the workload and align with institutional priorities and leadership interest.

Recommendation 2:

Capture, report, and communicate impact metrics annually as a complement to activity metrics. Use qualitative information to complement activity metrics.

Present selected impact metrics alongside activity metrics to add depth and context. Focus on the impact metrics that align with institutional priorities and leadership interest. Use a balance of quantitative and qualitative data and reporting techniques to convey a richer picture.

Recommendation 3:

Capture relevant quality or process improvement metrics. Report and communicate as needed.

Quality and process improvement metrics are very useful internally but larger audiences may not have strong interest. Use these metrics to improve research development operations but recognize that reporting incremental changes may be less important.

Conclusion

As institutions of higher education continue to prioritize research growth and competitiveness in the research enterprise, the ability to effectively assess and communicate the impact of research development becomes increasingly important. Traditional activity metrics, while useful, fall short in capturing the nuanced and often long-term contributions of research development professionals.

This article has outlined a conceptual framework for categorizing RD metrics, offered practical strategies for impact assessment, and identified key recommendations for professionals seeking to demonstrate value in a meaningful way. While challenges remain, these can be navigated using the guidance provided. Ultimately, advancing the practice of impact assessment in research development will strengthen the profession and help secure its vital role in supporting the research enterprise.

AUTHORS

Kimberly Eck, MPH, PhD has been working in research development for 16 years. She currently serves as the Sr. Associate Vice President of Research at Emory University where she launched the Office of Research Development and, previously, served as the Assistant Vice Chancellor for Research Development at the University of Tennessee. She is also the Sr. Director of the NORDP Consultants Program, which has worked with more than 170 emerging research institutions since 2022.

Karen Fischer, MBA has been working in research development for 15 years. She currently serves as the Director of Grants Resources and Services in the Office of Research and Innovation at Appalachian State University where she leverages RD impact metrics to enhance research success of the research development programming at App State. She created a proposal development program at an emerging research institution in a previous role. Fischer serves as a consultant in the NORDP Consultant Program, advising on best practices in research development and strategic funding approaches with emerging research institutions.

Enas Albatineh, Ph.D., is an Assistant Professor of Computer Science at Florida Memorial University. Her research focuses on artificial intelligence and information security. She holds a Ph.D. in Information Systems and brings expertise in business intelligence, data analytics, and system design. Dr. Albatineh also contributes to national STEM and cybersecurity initiatives and is dedicated to advancing innovative practices in higher education.

Aisha A. Alvarez, Ph.D., is the Director of AUC-GRANTED Operations at Spelman College, where she leads the implementation of the NSF-funded

AUC-GRANTED initiative—a cross-institutional collaboration among Spelman College, Morehouse College, Morehouse School of Medicine, and Clark Atlanta University. With over 15 years of experience spanning higher education, nonprofits, and the corporate sector, Dr. Alvarez brings deep expertise in research operations, multi-institutional strategy, and equity-centered leadership. In her role, she oversees day-to-day operations, shared infrastructure development, and strategic engagement to strengthen research capacity and collaboration across the Atlanta University Center.

Susan Carter, J.D. is an independent consultant and a NORDP Consultant. She was formerly the Director of Sponsored Research and Research Development at the Santa Fe Institute in Santa Fe, New Mexico as well as the Director of Research Development at the University of California Merced. She is a Charter Fellow of the National Organization of Research Development Professionals (NORDP) and was a founding member of the NORDP Board of Directors. She has consulted, published, and presented extensively on growing the research enterprise, assessment of research development practices, grant getting strategies, faculty development, diversity and broadening participation, and team scholarship.

Pamela A.G. Clarke is the Senior Director of Research Development at Howard University, where she leads campus-wide efforts to expand research capacity, strengthen faculty competitiveness, and build strategic research partnerships. She brings over a decade of experience in proposal development, interdisciplinary collaboration, and academic research strategy. With extensive experience across the pre-award grant lifecycle, she has successfully built collaborative partnerships with federal agencies, foundations, and industry.

Marta Collier-Youngblood, M.A. is the Special Assistant to the Vice President for Strategic Initiatives and Social Justice and the Director of the Office of Sponsored Programs and Research for Tougaloo College. She has 20 years of expertise in fundraising and education leadership and is also the Co-Founder and Senior Associate of Youngblood & Associates, LLC. She serves as a trusted consultant in education, nonprofit and workforce sectors specializing in Minority Serving Institutions and Emerging Research Institutions. Her passion centers around connecting organizations to the resources they need for advancing vital economic and community development goals. Her mission is to help organizations build creative and strategic solutions that are effective and sustainable.

Dorothy Daley, MS, CGMS is the Interim Director of Sponsored Programs at Kentucky State University. She has worked in Research Administration for over a decade both at the departmental and central level. She oversees both pre- and post-award activity along with research development.

Jayanta Das, PhD. is the Assistant Professor of Biology, Health and Natural Sciences at Florida Memorial University, Miami Gardens, FL is actively teaching and mentoring STEM students in south florida, in Radiobiology, toxicology, cancer stem cell biology and designing anticancer small molecules against cancer stem cell epigenetic reprogramming. Dr. Das is the PI of NSF EPIIC ASPIRE grant and made the successful research collaboration with other partner HBCUs. Dr. Das also demonstrated his research excellences in the field of antioxidant, molecular signaling pathways of cancer stem cells, anti-cancer drugs, apoptosis, and free radical research. [Full bio.](#)

Margaret Farrow is the Director of Research Development & Sponsored Programs at Spelman College. She brings almost 20 years of experience in grants administration, social science research, and programmatic evaluation to her current role. In her position, Ms. Farrow provides faculty and

staff with guidance and technical assistance to identify, secure, and administer grant funding in support of research, creative scholarship, student research training, and programmatic initiatives. The intersection of her formal education in physics & sociology juxtaposed to her vocational experience in programmatic evaluation and grant administration gives Ms. Farrow a unique perspective on how to effectively support researchers and scholars across diverse disciplines, from the humanities to the natural sciences.

Melissa A. Harrington, PhD has been at Delaware State University (DSU) since 2001 where she started as a faculty member in the Department of Biological Sciences. She currently serves as the Associate Vice President for Research and chief research officer in this role oversees research administration at DSU, and directs the Delaware Institute of Science and Technology, DSU's research institute.

Triscia W. Hendrickson, PhD is the Associate Provost for Research and Student Training at Morehouse College. In this role, she provides leadership to support and expand the Morehouse College research enterprise, enhance the institutional structure for undergraduate student training, and ensure research compliance for federally funded projects. She has served as PI or co-PI on several grants to support research development and student training, including the NIH-funded MARC U-STAR (T34GM096954), NSF-funded EAGER: Increasing HBCU Participation in NSF DRL Grant Opportunities (DRL-2131762), and the NSF-funded AUC-GRANTED: Advancing Transformation of the Research Enterprise through Shared Resource Support Model for Collective Impact and Synergistic Effect (OIA-2341110). Dr. Hendrickson is a tenured professor in the Biology Department at Morehouse College; she earned a BS in Biology from the University of the Virgin Islands and a PhD in Biochemistry, Cell and Developmental Biology from Emory University.

James Kohler, PhD has been working in grant writing efforts as team lead for over 20 years. He currently serves as the Director of Office Research Development (ORD) at Morehouse School of Medicine in Atlanta, Georgia. He successfully leads a 12-week Grant Writing course for junior faculty offered twice a year (Spring and Fall). In addition, the ORD coordinates a monthly seminar series to feature individual faculty research programs and Center programs; and Technical Assistance workshops to inform researchers of funding opportunities and/or resources available to assist them in writing their proposals

Rachel McBride-Montesdeoca, EdD currently leads the STEM Student Success Center at McMurry University, where she develops proactive advising strategies, supports underrepresented students in STEM, and designs learning initiatives. Her recent research has explored culturally responsive support structures and the role of identity and belonging in student retention, particularly for first-generation students. In addition to program leadership, she contributes to institutional-wide efforts to foster resilience and academic engagement.

Eric A. Mintz, PhD is a professor of chemistry and directs the Clark Atlanta University Research and Development Infrastructure (REDI) Project. He has over thirty years of experience working with faculty members on proposal development. He is currently focusing on faculty development in resource identification, proposal development, and submission, primarily for non-STEM faculty members.

Ishita Mukerji, PhD is the Associate Provost for Research at City College of New York. She recently joined this institution after a career as a faculty member and academic leader at a small liberal arts institution. She currently leads the Office of Research at CUNY and oversees grants administration, research facilities and compliance.

Marcia Straughn, PhD, RN, CNE is the programs director for the Patty Hanks Shelton School of Nursing at McMurry University in Abilene, Texas. She has held a number of roles in nursing education and administration over the last 15 years and served as PI for institutional level grants and Texas Higher Education Coordinating Board grants at Abilene Christian University. In addition to her current work in nursing education and as the PI for McMurry's Nursing Shortage Reduction Program grants, Dr. Straughn shares her experience in grants and research development with the community as a member of the Board of Directors and Vice President for Development of the Abilene Community Theater (ACT).

Kimberley R. Sudler, Ed.D, MBA is associate vice president for Academic Operations at Delaware State University. She has worked in the fields of institutional research and decision support for over 25 years. She developed and maintains a data and analytics platform to manage institutional performance and support process improvement initiatives. She is PI for two federal grants related to strengthening research capacity.

Christopher Theriot, DBA, CFRE is the Director of Grants and Resource Development Liaison at the University of West Alabama (UWA), a Joint Appointment between the Office of Sponsored Programs, Research and Outreach, and Institutional Advancement. He is a dedicated, proactive professional in the nonprofit/higher education industry, with over 25 years of leadership in raising over \$75 million in public and private funds for organizations providing critical resources for their designated communities.

Frances Williams, PhD is the Vice President for Research and Sponsored Programs at Clark Atlanta University (CAU). In this role, she is responsible for leading the research enterprise at CAU, including oversight of research grants, contracts, and technology transfer. She also leads initiatives to promote scholarly development of faculty, staff, and student researchers, enhance visibility of CAU

research, and establish strategic partnerships. She is a Professor in the Department of Cyber-Physical Systems.

Tamika S. Williamson, CPA, MBA is the Director of the Budgets and Contracts office at Spelman College where she leads the financial administration, compliance and strategic oversight of grants, gifts, donations, and the institution's overall budget. With expertise in data analytics, she focuses on strengthening reporting, improving decision-making processes and sound financial stewardship in the academic sector.

Alicia T. Wyatt, EdD has held a number of roles at McMurry University over the last 25 years: faculty member, Dean of Natural and Computational Sciences, and currently, Associate Vice President for Sponsored Programs and Research Compliance (SPARC). She has served as Project Director for two Title V grants and co-PI for two NSF grants. The SPARC office collaborates with Corporate and Foundation Relations, the Institutional Review Board, and supports professional development as well as pre- and post-award activity for federally sponsored projects at the institution.

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The background is a solid dark blue color. Overlaid on this are several sets of thin, white, curved lines that flow across the page, creating a sense of motion and depth. These lines are arranged in a way that they appear to be part of a larger, continuous pattern. In the lower right quadrant, there is a large, semi-transparent dark blue circle that partially overlaps the white lines.

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